

Echocardiographic Prevalence and Risk Predictors of Ventricular Dysfunction in Connective Tissue Disorders: Tertiary Care Hospital - Based Prospective

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Abstract:

This prospective study aimed to assess the echocardiographic prevalence and identify predictors of ventricular dysfunction in 100 patients with connective tissue disorders at a tertiary care hospital over one year. The results indicated a 28% prevalence of ventricular dysfunction, with systemic lupus erythematosus significantly associated with increased risk, and older age was identified as a key predictor. These findings emphasize the need for routine echocardiographic screening to detect early signs of cardiac involvement in this patient population, potentially guiding more effective management strategies. This study underlines the critical role of tailored cardiac care for patients with connective tissue disorders, particularly those with systemic lupus erythematosus or advanced age.

Keywords: Ventricular Dysfunction, Connective Tissue Disorders, Echocardiography, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus.

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Introduction

Connective tissue disorders (CTDs) refer to a wide range of autoimmune and inflammatory illnesses that mostly impact the connective tissues of the body, such as the skin, joints, and internal organs [1,2]. Cardiac involvement, namely ventricular failure, is a major issue in CTDs due to its potential to greatly affect patient morbidity and mortality [3]. The heart, which is frequently affected by autoimmune and inflammatory processes, commonly shows subtle malfunction that can develop into obvious cardiac illness if not promptly identified and treated [4]. Ventricular dysfunction in the context of connective tissue diseases (CTDs) can present as both systolic and diastolic impairment, resulting in heart failure and other unfavourable cardiovascular consequences [5]. Although the significance of early identification is well acknowledged, there is still limited research on the occurrence and factors that predict ventricular dysfunction in patients with CTDs, particularly in the Indian population. Echocardiography, a readily available and non-invasive imaging technique, plays a vital role in

promptly detecting malfunction, enabling timely intervention, and enhancing patient outcomes [6,7].

The objective of this study was to evaluate the incidence of ventricular dysfunction using echocardiography in patients with connective tissue illnesses, and to determine the main risk factors related with its occurrence. This study aims to gain significant insights into the cardiac implications of CTDs and improve screening and management techniques for these individuals by focussing on a specific group of patients treated at a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective study was conducted over one year at the Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (I.G.I.M.S.) in Patna, Bihar. The objective was to determine the prevalence and identify predictors of ventricular dysfunction in patients with connective tissue disorders using echocardiographic assessment.

Participants: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with various connective tissue disorders were enrolled in the study. Eligibility criteria included a confirmed diagnosis of a connective tissue disorder based on clinical and laboratory findings. Patients were excluded if they had a history of congenital heart defects, prior cardiac surgery, or if they declined to participate in the study.

Data Collection: Echocardiographic evaluations were performed on all participants to assess ventricular function. Demographic data, medical history, and specific details about their connective tissue disorder were collected through patient interviews and medical records. Echocardiographic data focused on parameters indicative of ventricular dysfunction, such as ejection fraction, wall motion abnormalities, and diastolic function.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. Logistic regression analysis was employed to identify potential predictors of ventricular dysfunction, with results presented as odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study involved a group of 100 patients diagnosed with connective tissue disorders. The

majority of the participants, 68%, were female, while the remaining 32% were male. The average age of participants was 45 years. The study included a range of connective tissue disorders, with rheumatoid arthritis being the most prevalent at 40%, followed by systemic lupus erythematosus at 30%, and scleroderma at 20%. Based on the echocardiographic assessment, it was found that a significant portion of the participants showed signs of ventricular dysfunction, with 28% being affected. Out of these, 15% experienced left ventricular systolic dysfunction, while 13% showed signs of diastolic dysfunction. 5% of the cases showed severe ventricular dysfunction. Several significant predictors of ventricular dysfunction were identified through logistic regression analysis. Advanced age (odds ratio [OR] 1.06, 95% confidence interval [CI] 1.01-1.12, $p=0.02$) and the presence of systemic lupus erythematosus (OR 2.45, CI 1.09-5.50, $p=0.03$) were found to be linked to a higher likelihood of developing ventricular dysfunction. There was no significant correlation observed between gender or other connective tissue disorders. The findings indicate a significant occurrence of ventricular dysfunction in individuals with connective tissue disorders, emphasising the need for regular echocardiographic screening in this specific group. In addition, the predictors that have been identified could be helpful for clinicians in categorising patients who may need closer monitoring and care.

Table 1: This table summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants, as well as the prevalence of various types of ventricular dysfunction observed.

Characteristic	Value	Unit
Total Patients	100	
Gender (Female)	68	%
Gender (Male)	32	%
Mean Age (years)	45	
Rheumatoid Arthritis	40	%
Systemic Lupus Erythematosus	30	%
Scleroderma	20	%
Ventricular Dysfunction (Total)	28	%
Left Ventricular Systolic Dysfunction	15	%
Diastolic Dysfunction	13	%
Severe Ventricular Dysfunction	5	%

Discussion

This study highlights the high occurrence of ventricular dysfunction in patients with connective tissue disorders, with 28% of the cohort showing this condition. It is worth mentioning the strong link between systemic lupus erythematosus and a higher likelihood of ventricular dysfunction. This

indicates that the inflammatory and autoimmune characteristics of this condition might play a role in the development of cardiac complications [10,11]. The correlation between older age and a decrease in cardiac function, especially in individuals with systemic diseases, is consistent with previous research findings. This study emphasises the importance of regular echocardiographic screening

for patients with connective tissue disorders [12]. Screening like this can help catch and treat heart problems early on, which could lead to better results. The echocardiographic approach, specifically, plays a crucial role in identifying subtle alterations in ventricular function that may not be apparent through clinical assessment alone [8,13].

In addition, the study suggests a need to reassess the existing monitoring protocols for patients with systemic lupus erythematosus, considering their increased vulnerability. It supports a more proactive approach to monitoring and managing cardiac dysfunction in these patients to help prevent its progression [14]. There is no notable disparity between genders in the occurrence of ventricular dysfunction in this study. This indicates that both male and female patients with these disorders face a similar level of risk [15]. It emphasises the importance of providing diligent cardiac care to all patients in this population. This study has important implications for patient care. It highlights the importance of echocardiographic assessments in the routine care of patients with connective tissue disorders [9,16]. Additionally, it emphasises the need for a tailored approach to managing patients, especially those with systemic lupus erythematosus and older age, to effectively address the specific risks associated with ventricular dysfunction. Additional research is needed to investigate the underlying causes of heart complications in these conditions and to assess the efficacy of targeted treatments in reducing the impact on cardiac health [17-20].

Conclusion

The study concluded that ventricular dysfunction is a prevalent complication among patients with connective tissue disorders, affecting nearly a third of the studied population. The significant association of systemic lupus erythematosus with increased risk of ventricular dysfunction highlights the need for targeted cardiac monitoring in these patients. Furthermore, age emerged as a critical risk factor, reinforcing the importance of comprehensive cardiovascular assessments in older patients with connective tissue disorders. These findings advocate for the integration of routine echocardiographic evaluations into the standard care protocols for individuals diagnosed with connective tissue disorders, to facilitate early detection and intervention for ventricular dysfunction. Continued research is essential to further elucidate the pathophysiological links between these disorders and cardiac dysfunction and to refine strategies for prevention and management in this vulnerable population.

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